

EMPOWERMENT AND EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS IN RELATION TO FAMILY ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of family environment on empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls. The descriptive survey design was used for the present study. A sample of 200 adolescent girls studying in schools of Mohali district was raised by employing simple random sampling technique. The data for the study were collected using the standardized tools; Adolescent Girls Empowerment Scale (AGES) by Sisodia and Singh (2009), Emotional Competence Scale by Bharadwaj and Sharma (1998) and Family Climate Scale by Shah (2010). The collected data were analyzed with the help of Pearson correlation coefficient. The investigator also tried to find differences in empowerment and Emotional Competence of adolescent girls' in relation to their family environment. The findings of the study revealed that there are significant differences in the empowerment of adolescent girls in relation to their family environment. However no significant differences were found in the emotional competence of adolescent girls in relation to their family environment. These results enable teachers to understand and emphasise the role of family environment in empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls.

Keywords: Empowerment, Emotional Competence, Family Environment

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INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is the transitional period of human life that requires special attention and protection. During this period the family provides the most vital and formidable environment for the cognitive, emotional, and social development of adolescents. The family is the oldest

and the most important of all the institutions that man has devised to regulate and integrate behaviour of an adolescent as he strives to satisfy his basic needs. The family is basically a unit in which parents and children's live together. Its key position rests on its multiple functions in relation to overall development of his members, their protection and overall well being. Therefore it would emerge that not only the social and physical well being of the individual is taken care of by the family, but the psychological well being as well.

Family environment refers to all sorts of moral and ethical values, emotional, social and intellectual climate set up by the family members to contribute to the wholesome development. The richness of family environment is reflected in the attitude of the child. Family environment has been recognized as vital factor in moulding personality of the child. In India families, parent child relationship is the most important constituent of family environment. In India, a girl is raised with inferior status and lesser privileges as compared to the male child which may be considered as basis of her weaker empowerment. Mahatma Gandhi said, "If you educate a man you educate an individual, but if you educate a woman you educate a family". When the girls are empowered, they transform their own life and lives of communities. As family and school environment plays a significant role in empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls, the investigator found it appropriate to study the relationship between empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls and their family environment.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Family Environment and Empowerment of Adolescent Girls

Deepsikha and Bhanot (2011) assessed the impact of family environment of one hundred adolescent girls on their socio-emotional adjustment. It was revealed that all the eight family environment factors, viz. cohesion, expressiveness conflict, acceptance and caring, independence, active-recreational orientation, organization and control together showed significant role in socio-emotional and educational adjustment of adolescent girls.

Shabana et al. (2014) conducted a study on adolescent girls 'empowerment and found that rural government schools adolescent girls are less empowered than their counterparts in urban government schools in almost all the dimensions of empowerment.

Bhagabati & Dutta (2019) in a study conducted on Decision Making And Empowerment of Adolescent Girls also concluded that rural adolescent girls are less empowered than urban adolescent girls on decision making.

Bansal (2016) found the positive correlation between the family environment and self-efficacy of adolescents in a study conducted on 403 adolescents (223 boys and 185 girls) studying in various schools of Telangana State.

Rani et al. (2021) found that out of 160 parents, (79%) of them had low parental perceptions and attitudes of empowerment of their adolescent girls.

Family Environment and emotional competence of Adolescent Girls

Lau and Kwok (2000) concluded that a cohesive, orderly and achieving family environment is conducive to more positive development among adolescents, in terms of lower depression and higher self-concept.

Chakra and Prabha (2004) found that family environment had significant influence on the emotional competence of adolescents. Cohesion, conflict, acceptance and caring in personal growth dimensions were found to have significant positive influence on emotional competence of adolescents and organization and control dimensions of family environment had no significant influence on emotional competence of adolescents.

Arunmozhi and Rajendran (2008) assessed the influence of age, material status, type of family, community and emotional intelligence of 305 women self help group members. The investigator concluded that the self help group member do not differ in their emotional intelligence based on their age, marital status, type of family, community and family status.

Sharma and Sahani (2013) conducted study on a sample of 300 adolescents to find emotional competence in relation to home environment and personality of adolescents

Results revealed that adolescents' emotional competence was in moderate level. Further significant independent effect of home environment and personality on emotional competence was noticed.

Kunjilata, & Kaberi (2019) analysed the relationship between the home environment and the emotional competence of 120 adolescents. The results indicate that reward and

permissiveness dimensions of home environment predict emotional competence of the child.
33.6% variance

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the empowerment of adolescent girls In relation to family environment.
2. To study the emotional competence of adolescent girls in relation to family environment.
3. To compare Empowerment of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups.
4. To compare emotional competence of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups.

HYPOTHESES

H01. There exists no significant relationship between family environment and empowerment of adolescent girls.

H02. There exists no significant relationship between family environment and emotional competence of adolescent girls.

H03. There exists no significant difference in empowerment of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad family environment groups.

H04. There exists no significant difference in emotional competence of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad family environment groups.

METHOD

The study has been conducted by the descriptive survey method.

Kelly's method was used.to categorize the adolescent girl students in good and bad family environment group, Top 27% (54) cases formed good family environment group and bottom 27% (54) cases formed bad family environment group. t–test was employed to the study difference between empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad family environment groups. The technique of correlation was employed to study the relationship between empowerment and emotional competence.

SAMPLE

The sample consisted of 200 adolescent girl selected randomly studying in the Government schools of Mohali District. The technique of random sampling was used for the present study. al competence of adolescent girl in relation to family environment.

TOOLS USED

1. Family climate scale (FCC) by Shah (2010).
2. Adolescent Girls' Empowerment Scale (AGE) by Sisodia and Singh (2009).
3. Scale of Emotional Competence by Bhardwaj and Sharma (1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the results of Pearson coefficient of correlation to study the relationship between empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls in relation to family environment.

Table 1

Coefficient of Correlation between Empowerment, Emotional Competence and Family Environment of adolescent girls (N = 200)

Variables	N	Coefficient of Correlation (r)
Empowerment and Family Environment	200	0.370**
Emotional Competence and Family Environment	200	0.063 (ns)

NOTE:-

1. $r = 0.138$ to be significant at 0.05 level.
2. $r = 0.181$ to be significant at 0.01 level.

Table-1 shows that calculated value of coefficient of correlation (r) between Family Environment and Empowerment of adolescent girls is 0.370, which is more than table value of 0.181 and hence significant at 0.01 level.

Therefore, **Hypothesis-H01:- "There exists no significant relationship between Family Environment and Empowerment of Adolescent Girls"** is not accepted. It means Family Environment has significant relationship with Empowerment of Adolescent Girls.

The finding is supported by studies conducted by Deepsikha and Bhanot(2011), Shabana et.al.(2014), Bansal(2016). Hence good family environment make the adolescent girls more powerful and empowered

Table-1 also shows that coefficient of correlation (r) between Family Environment and Emotional Competence of adolescent girls is 0.063, which is less than the table value of 0.138 and hence not significant.

Therefore, **Hypothesis-H02:- "There exists no significant relationship between Family Environment and Emotional Competence of Adolescent Girls"** is accepted. It means Family Environment has not significant relationship with Emotional Competence of Adolescent Girls.

This means family environment does not affect emotional competence of an adolescent. It may be due to the fact that emotional competence is an inherent trait and that's why it may not have been influenced by family environment. It may be considered as inherent property of an adolescent.

Table 2 presents result of t-test to the study the difference between empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad family environment groups.

Table 2

t-value for significance of difference between mean scores of empowerment and emotional competence of adolescent girls in good and bad family environment groups (N = 108)

Variables	Groups	N	Mean score	df	Std Dev	t- value
Empowerment	Good family environment	54	185.31	106	22.12	6.449**
	Bad family environment	54	155.39		25.95	
Emotional Competence	Good family environment	54	100.72	106	12.44	1.670 (ns)
	Bad family environment	54	95.44		19.61	

** = Significant at 0.01 level

ns = not-significant

NOTE:-

1. t = 1.98 to be significant at 0.05 level for 106 degree of freedom.
2. t = 2.62 to be significant at 0.01 level for 106 degree of freedom.

Table 2 shows t value of 6.449 for df = 106 between Empowerment and Family Environment of adolescent girls which is more than table value of 1.98, hence found to be significant at 0.01 level of significance. On the basis of this result, we can conclude that there is significant

difference between the empowerment of adolescent girls belonging to good and bad family environment groups.

Therefore, **Hypothesis-H03:- "There exists no significant difference in Empowerment of Adolescent Girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups."** is not accepted. It means there exists significant difference in Empowerment of Adolescent Girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups.

Since the mean score of good family environment group (185.31) is higher than the mean score of bad family environment group (155.39). Therefore, adolescent girls belonging to good family environment group are more empowered than adolescent girls belonging to bad family environment group.

The finding is supported by studies conducted by Deepsikha and Bhanot (2011), Shabana et.al. (2014), Bansal (2016), Bhagabati&Dutta(2019). Hence good family environment makes adolescent girls more empowered in comparison to bad family environment.

Table 2 shows calculated t value of 1.670 for $df = 106$ between Emotional Competence and Family Environment of adolescent girls is less than the table value of 1.98, hence found to be not significant.

Therefore, **Hypothesis-H04:- —There exists no significant difference in Emotional Competence of Adolescent Girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups."** is accepted. It means there does not exist significant difference in Emotional Competence of Adolescent Girls belonging to good and bad Family Environment groups.

The finding is supported by studies conducted by Chakra and Prabha (2004), Arunmozhi and Rajendran (2008) and Kaberi&Kunjata(2019).

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The results of present study hold manifold implications for the teachers, parents and counselors. The finding that family environment is significant factor in empowering adolescent girls enables teachers to understand and emphasize the role of family environment in empowerment of adolescent girls. It also brings to fore the need of educating parents to make them realize their role and need of providing conducive family environment to adolescent girls. It also helps guidance worker in relating empowerment problem of

adolescent girls to family environment. The school administration should also hold frequent Parent Teachers' Meets to guide parents to improve their relationships with adolescent girls and parents should also be educated about the importance of good family environment in making adolescent girls empowered for their bright future in such meetings. The results also indicate that emotional competence of adolescent girls is multidimensional and teachers must be empathetic to the problems of adolescent girls. Teachers and counselors should educate parents about the need of providing conducive family environment by relating emotional competence problem of adolescent girls to family environment.

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